

PROGRESSIVE EDUCATION UNDER TRANSFORMATIVE LEADERSHIP AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT OF SCHOOL HEADS

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ABSTRACT

Transformative leadership is one of the progressive indicators in the 21st century educational system where school heads innovate and reinvent progressive styles in managing and leading their subordinates towards efficiency and productivity of public service. This study described and examined school heads transformative leadership and organizational commitment. The study utilized descriptive correlational research and participated by 50 randomly selected public secondary school heads in the Schools Division of Bulacan. Results revealed that school heads highly practiced innovative leadership as they manage, lead and supervise their schools. They utilized strategic thinking, innovative thinking and put greater consistency in leading their subordinates. On the other hand, school heads' exercised continuance organizational commitment where they highly recognize the significance of their roles and functions as school leaders as ultimate basis why they still stay and continually serve the community and the public at large in the education sector. Conclusively, development of action-related leadership skills may a critical factor for enhancing organizational commitment in leadership and supervision of school heads.

Keywords: *transformative, leadership, styles, school heads, organization, commitment*

INTRODUCTION

School heads are stewards of schools where they are entrusted with full trust and confidence to manage and lead the school effectively. In the ever-evolving educational landscape, school administration and governance require intensive leadership as schools are regarded as the citadel of formal learning. In recent years, it is not only confined with the manner and means of leadership and governance principles instituted by the school leaders in the schools but also extends the practical application of innovative leadership and attitudes which are tantamount to progressive leadership.

School Leadership remains as the cornerstone of the effective instruction and meaningful learning experiences. Education as an investment constitutes the largest enterprises. The concept of school administration and school resources are the foundation of school sources (Usman, 2016). With the effective school leadership and governance, schools develop a dynamic and future oriented sustainability (Cranston, 2021). The development of educational leaders' innovative leadership practices is parallel to the development of school as formalized institution.

Innovative school leadership is one of the progressive indicators in the 21st century educational system where school heads innovate and reinvent progressive styles in managing and leading their subordinates towards efficiency and productivity of public service. In the Philippine educational settings, school heads perform supervisory and managerial tasks who spearhead the school and drive its programs and activities in the attainment of school's goals and objectives and in general, achievement of national educational goals. Innovative leadership is constituted in the interplay between hierarchical and distributed dimensions to obtain work efficiency (Vennebo, 2021).

School leaders' practices support innovative use of resources in the achievement of effective instruction leading to quality-based education and efficient public service in the field of education (Hakansson- Lindqvist, 2019). Innovative leadership and leadership for improvement include extensive opportunities reflecting the experiences of teachers and school administrators. Leadership learning outcomes contain effective leadership practices which create more impactful programs and activities (Drysdale et al., 2021). School administrators' innovative and transformational leadership practices both play significant role in the development of school (Zainal and Matore, 2021).

Research Questions

This study described and examined school heads' transformative leadership styles and their organizational commitment. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. How may school heads transformative leadership styles be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 strategic thinking;
 - 1.2 innovative thinking; and
 - 1.3 action patterns?

2. How may school heads' organizational commitment be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 affective;
 - 2.2 continuance; and
 - 2.3 normative?
3. Is there a significant relationship between school heads' transformative styles and their organizational commitment?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a descriptive correlational research and researcher-made survey-questionnaire was used in order to describe and examine school heads' transformative leadership styles and organizational commitment. Apparently, the study randomly selected the participation of 50 public secondary school heads among 50 public schools across in the Schools Division of Bulacan. Verbal consent was secured by the researchers. On the other hand, survey-questionnaire as the main research instrument was subjected to reliability testing which obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of .817 which signified that the instrument was acceptable. Meanwhile, as to the actual administration of survey-questionnaire, Google Forms was used in which data contained in the same platform was downloaded and organized by the researchers. Relevant statistical tools were used such as frequency, mean, overall mean, standard deviation and Pearson R in order to describe and examine the school heads' innovative leadership practices and organizational commitment.

Apparently, the researchers implemented higher level of ethical standards in conducting this study where they concealed the identities of the respondents including their email addresses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. School Heads' Transformative Leadership Styles

Table 1.

School Heads' Transformative Leadership Styles in terms of strategic thinking, innovative thinking and action patterns

Items	M	VI
Strategic Thinking	3.14	Agree
Innovative Thinking	3.38	Strongly Agree
Action Patters	3.53	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.00-3.25-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.24-2.50-Agree (A), 2.49-1.50-Disagree (D), 1.00-1.75-Strongly Disagree (SDA)

As shown in Table 1, the summary of all the items or indicators under the three variables used on transformative leadership styles. Based from the results, school heads' innovative leadership practices in terms of strategic thinking, it obtains an overall mean

of 3.14 which is verbally described as “Agree.” This indicates that school heads are actively engaged in strategic planning where they create realistic programs and activities for the development of their schools. In addition, school heads spearhead active consultation where they design effective programs through practical and consultative approaches. On the other hand, school heads’ innovative leadership practices in terms of innovative thinking obtains an overall mean of 3.38 which is verbally described as “Agree.” This implies that school heads are immensely committed in introducing positive change through innovation and practice. Further, the result also shows that school heads utilize reality-based principles and creativity as ground indicators of innovative leadership practices. School heads foster creativity in every program they implement so that they can be able to inspire their subordinates in making school activities practically significant to the lives of their learners, teachers and of the community in general. Lastly, school heads innovative leadership styles in terms of action patterns obtains an overall mean of 3.53 which is verbally described as “Strongly Agree.” This signifies that school heads are strongly committed to implementing effective and ethical leadership practices as they are goal-oriented leaders who take significant action to institute positive change in their school and community. In addition, the school heads are strongly committed to prioritized schools’ objectives which are reflected through sustainable actions as reinforced by innovative styles in implementing school programs and activities.

The findings reveal that practical significance of transformative leadership styles as characterized by school heads in terms of strategic thinking, innovative thinking and action patterns, enable their schools develop and abide with the progressive changes in the entire educational landscape. In this line, school heads are inclined with transformative leadership practices which address pressing concerns in the education system as faced by their school. Transformative leadership styles of school heads are commonly characterized by collaboration, comprehensive planning and consistent action patterns (de Jong et al., 2021). Innovative work behaviors of teachers and school heads are important for school’s effectiveness. Also, school principals are compelled to utilize innovative leadership in order to articulate and characterize progressive leadership and management of the school (Khaola and Oni, 2020).

2.School Heads’ Organizational Commitment

Table 2.
School Heads’ Organizational Commitment in terms of affective, continuance and normative commitment

Action Patters	3.54	Strongly Agree
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Legend: 4.00-3.25-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.24-2.50-Agree (A), 2.49-1.50-Disagree (D), 1.00-1.75-Strongly Disagree (SDA)

As shown in Table 2, the summary of all the items or indicators under the three variables used along with organizational commitment. Organizational commitment is the level of engagement and dedication of school heads as they serve as the stewards of the

school where they are also expected to dispense effective and efficient leadership and governance in the public service under education sector. Based from the results, school heads' organizational commitment in terms of affective commitment obtains an overall mean of 3.53 which is verbally described as "Strongly Agree." This indicates that school heads pose strong emotional attachment forming their commitment to stay and serve the school. Also, school heads possess love for their roles as leaders in the school and feel strong sense of belongingness which directly reflect their deep- seated connection to work and thrive for the betterment of the schools they serve. On the other hand, in terms of continuance commitment, it obtains an overall mean of 3.55 which is verbally described as "Strongly Agree." This implies that school heads perceive their roles as significant and noble contributing to their strong commitment as public servants. Also, school heads are engaged in school as their second home which emphasize that school heads put personal investments with their roles and functions specifically their strong emotional attachment. Lastly, in terms of normative commitment, it obtains an overall mean of 3.54 which verbally described as "Strongly Agree." This shows that school heads' sense of obligation and duty are reflective with their strong commitment to serve the school and the community. In addition, school heads few options of leaving the schools imply that school head perceived limited options on leaving the school which on serve and fulfill their roles and responsibilities as school heads.

The findings show that school heads show strong and founded organizational commitment characterized by their strong ties (affective), recognition of their significance of their roles (continuance) and sense of obligation (normative). Thus, strong commitment of school heads molded them as good and efficient leaders who embrace responsibilities and challenges just to serve the public more particularly in providing quality-based education. School leaders are considered as effective leaders when they embrace strong organizational commitment, work values and leadership behavior (Jones, 2020). Same as the result of the study of Pastrana et.al (2021), Teachers regard more value on organizational commitment in the new normal setting in terms of continuance commitment rather than in affective and normative commitments. Teachers perceived school heads in public secondary schools often demonstrate school leadership behavior in initiating structure and consideration on their organizational commitment (Mendoza, 2023).

2. Relationship Between School Heads' Transformative Leadership Styles and Organizational Commitment

Table 3.
Relationship Between School Heads' Transformative Leadership Styles and Organizational Commitment

School Heads' Transformative Leadership Styles	Organizational Commitment		
	Affective	Continuance	Normative
Strategic Thinking	0.021	0.142	0.079
Innovative Thinking	0.885	0.327	0.585
	50	50	50
	0.154	-0.141	-0.272
	0.285	0.329	0.056

	50	50	50
Action Patterns	0.157	.305*	0.008
	0.276	0.032	0.958
	50	50	50

Legend: **-Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed)
*-Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Findings revealed that action patterns is positively correlated with continuance commitment which suggests that leaders who may exhibit strong action-oriented behaviors may enhance the perception of the conditions associated with leaving the organization thereby increasing their commitment. The results imply that development of action-related leadership skills may a critical factor for enhancing organizational commitment in leadership and supervision of school heads. The significant relationship observed with action patters also shows that proactive leadership may create an environment where school heads feel more committed. Thus, the results supported the study of Kim (2022) which asserts that Transformational leadership significantly implicated organizational commitment of school leaders. Thus, the study also showed that bureaucratic culture has the lowest innovative organizational impact.

Conclusions

School heads highly practiced transformative leadership as they manage, lead and supervise their schools. They utilized strategic thinking, innovative thinking and put greater consistency in leading their subordinates. On the other hand, school heads' exercised continuance organizational commitment where they highly recognize the significance of their roles and functions as school leaders as ultimate basis why they still stay and continually serve the community and the public at large in the education sector. Conclusively, development of action-related leadership skills may a critical factor for enhancing organizational commitment in leadership and supervision of school heads.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this research, researchers have adhered to the highest ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were also assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any moment. The anonymity of every respondent was rigorously protected throughout the study. Researchers have taken every precaution to ensure that the respondents' well-being was not compromised. Researchers confirm that there are no conflicts of interest that could potentially influence the outcomes of this study. Plagiarism in all forms was strictly avoided to maintain academic integrity. The interpretation of the findings was conducted without any bias, ensuring an objective

perspective. Lastly, it is important to state that the results from this research will be used solely for academic purposes.

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